

Demonstrating solar hydrogen evolution using thiomolybdate-modified carbon nitrides in a mass transport intensified 3 L loop photoreactor – A feasibility study

(Supporting Information)

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The draft tube is fixed in from the top and bottom in the middle part using two 3D printed draft tube holders (8) and two connecting rods with M4 threads (9) using M4 screws. Bottom and top part are connected to the middle part using two quick release fasteners (10). The reactor parts are sealed using two silicon O-rings (11) placed in the groves of the middle part. The SLPR is equipped with a stirring rod (12) with four 3D printed stirrers (13) mounted equally spaced along the draft tube and a bottom stirrer (14) mounted below the lower draft tube holder in the bottom part of the reactor. The stirring rod is fixed within a magnetic stirrer coupling (15) which is mounted at the top part of the SLPR. Using a coupling joint (16) the magnetic stirrer coupling can be connected to a laboratory stirrer. The cooling jacked (liquid cooling using a cryostat) enables reactor tempering and prevents the evaporation of the reaction solution during long term operation. The modular draft tube was implemented to ensure accessibility of the reactor tube for cleaning and modifications.

Table 1: SLPR glass and peripheral components.

Nr.	Component	Manufacturer	Reference
1	DN 100 LF cover low design, without groove	DWK Life Sciences	CLFL100
2	NS 29/32 Conical ground joints	NORMAG	CNSS2942
3	GL 18 screwthread tubes	DWK Life Sciences	CGL018
4	DN 100 LF pipe section, with groove	DWK Life Sciences	CLFW100
5	DURAN® tubing draft tube Ø 46 mm	SCHOTT	D04623
6	DURAN® tubing reactor tube Ø 100 mm	SCHOTT	D10025
7	DURAN® tubing cooling jacked Ø 150 mm	SCHOTT	D15030
8	DN 100 LF quick release fastener	DWK Life Sciences	CQ100-L
9	Silicon O-Ring	DWK Life Sciences	292254602
10	Draft tube holder	3D printed	drafttube_holder.stl
11	Stainless steel connecting rods	Custom made	connecting_rod.stl
12	600 mm Stirring Rod	Bola	C472-20
13	Stirrer draft tube	3D printed	stirrer_drafttube.stl
14	Stirrer bottom part	3D printed	stirrer_bottom.stl
15	Magnetic coupling	Bola	C520-24

2.1 Setup Components for Solar Trials

Figure 1: Flow chart of the stirred loop photoreactor setup (right) and corresponding experimental setup (left). PR: Stirred Loop Photoreactor, SC: Solar Collector, GS: gas scrubber, V1: check valve (gas), V2: two-way valve (gas), V3: two-way valve (gas), V4: two-way valve (liquid exhaust), V5: 3-way valve (gas), μ GC: micro gas chromatograph, C1: computer.

Figure 2 depicts a flow chart of the SLPR setup (left) and a picture of the physical setup (right) used for the trials. All of the used setup components are listed in Table 2. Argon gas was supplied both as carrier gas for the micro gas chromatograph (μ GC) and purge gas for hydrogen detection. Therefore, the argon supply line (5 bar) is split with a T-connector into two inert gas streams (Argon in). One stream is directly connected to the carrier port of the μ GC, the other stream is supplied to the mass flow controller (MFC) to regulate the purge gas flow directed towards the SLPR. Since the SLPR operates at slight overpressure, the MFC is protected using a check valve (V1) to prevent liquid pushback into the argon line. The MFC is connected to the SLPR using 8 m 1/8" FEP tubing. Manual two-way valves (V2/V3) are placed directly after the MFC and in front of the SLPR to prevent liquid flow into the FEP tubing if no argon flow is supplied and in case of V1 failure for instrument protection. The FEP tubing is connected to the bottom part of the SLPR using a GL 18 screw joint. The purge gas passes the reactor and is diverted at the top part of the SLPR through 8 m FEP tubing (GL 18 screw joint connection) into a gas scrubber (GS) filled with molecular sieve to prevent liquid vapor being carried towards the sample line of the μ GC. The GS is connected to the sample port of the μ GC for continuous hydrogen detection. A manual 3-way valve (V5) is placed between the GC and the μ GC as pressure relieve to prevent instrument damage in case of excessive overpressure. A manual GL 18 2-Way Stopcock (V4) is connected to the bottom part of the reactor as liquid exhaust to empty the SLPR after operation.

Table 2: Instrumentation and peripheral components used for solar hydrogen trials.

Nr.	Flowchart Reference	Component	Manufacturer	Reference
1	μGC	Micro Gas Chromatograph	Qmicro B.V.	DynamiQ-S
2	MFC	Mass flow controller	Sensirion	SFC5500-0.5slm
3	V1	Check valve	Swagelok	SS-2C-1
4	-	FEP Tubing 1/8"	Bola	S1815-08
5	-	Fitting flangeless for 1/8" tubing	Fischer Scientific	12942129
6	V2/V3	PTFE two-way-valve	Bola	F730-04 A
7	-	HT Laboratory Screw Joints 1/8" tubing GL 18	Bola	D629-42
8	GS	Gas scrubber	Bola	N1662-24 A
9	-	Molecular sieve 3A	Thermo Scientific	CAS: 308080-99-1
10	V4	GL 18 2-Way Stopcock	Bola	E684-18 A
11	V5	Miniature 3-Way Stopcocks	Bola	F731-08 A
12	-	GL 18 screw cap	Bola	CS018HT
13	-	GL 18 olives bent	Bola	D582-04
14	-	SLPR holder	3D printed	SLPR_holder.stl
15	-	Overhead stirrer	Steinberg Systems	SBS-LAB-126

2.2 Combined Diffuse/Specular Solar Collector

Table 3: Combined specular/diffuse collector components.

Nr.	Component	Manufacturer	Reference
1	Wooden frame	Custom made	-
2	Collector frame	3D printed	SLPR_SC.stl
3	PTFE reflector	GORE	Diffuse Reflector
4	coated aluminum collector	alanod	MIROSUN 20901L
5	UV sensor	Apogee Instruments	Apogee-SU-205-SS

3 Catalyst Preparation and Characterization

3.1 $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ Preparation

Melamine (99%, Sigma-Aldrich) and methanol (99.9%, VWR) were used as received. Heptazine-based polymeric carbon nitride (PCN) was synthesized by thermal condensation of 45 g melamine at 550 °C for 4 h in a covered crucible, using a heating rate of 10 °C min⁻¹. After cooling to room temperature, the resulting yellow solid was washed with deionized water, dried, and finely ground using an agate mortar.

For deposition of the co-catalyst, 30 g of the as-prepared PCN were dispersed in 1800 mL methanol, covered, and sonicated for 180 min. Subsequently, 0.9 g Na₂[Mo₃S₁₃]·5H₂O, previously dissolved in 200 mL methanol, was added slowly to the dispersion under continuous stirring. The resulting mixture was stirred for more than 20 h.

After completion of the deposition process, the catalyst was recovered by filtration and centrifugation, washed three times with deionized water, and dried at 70 °C overnight. Finally, the dried material was ground to obtain the final photocatalyst.

3.2 $\{\text{Mo}_3\}\text{-CN}_x$ Preparation and SEM/EDX Characterization

The surface morphology, chemical composition, and elemental distribution of the Mo₃S₁₃-PCN were analyzed using a ZEISS LEO 1550 VP scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) from Ametek, USA. The SEM was operated at an acceleration voltage of 15 kV. To prepare the sample for SEM imaging, a few milligrams of the Mo₃S₁₃-PCN material were dispersed in 1.0 mL of ethanol using sonication for 10 min. Subsequently, a thin film of the sample was obtained by drop-casting a few microliters of the suspended sample onto a conductive Ti foil substrate and allowed to dry at room temperature. To improve the conductivity and achieve higher resolution SEM imaging,

a 20 nm thick layer of Au was sputtered onto the sample surface. For EDS mapping, the samples were not sputtered with Au to avoid interference during the determination of Mo.

The SEM images (Figure 3a and b) reveal that the Mo_3S_{13} phase is composed of elongated rod- and blade-like structures, extending to the micrometer scale in length and featuring relatively flat surfaces. These elongated Mo_3S_{13} particles are densely packed and intergrown, forming a loosely stacked, hierarchical assembly with significant interparticle voids. In addition to the primary rods, smaller platelet- and fragment-like Mo_3S_{13} domains are observed decorating

Figure 2: SEM images of (a,b) $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and (c,d) Mo_3S_{13} -PCN photocatalyst at different magnifications.

the surfaces and edges of the larger structures, indicating a secondary nucleation or partial exfoliation process. This morphology suggests a layered growth mechanism, characteristic of Mo_3S_{13} materials, where stacked lamellae preferentially extend along specific crystallographic directions. The resulting architecture provides a high density of exposed edges, which is beneficial for catalytic applications, as these sites are commonly associated with enhanced activity in MoS-based systems. Figure 3 c and d show the SEM images of polymeric carbon nitride after mixing with $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$, where a layered structure with a rough surface and agglomerated, irregular particles is observed. Notably, the elongated $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$

rods remain clearly distinguishable and are intimately associated with the polymeric carbon nitride particles, indicating successful incorporation of $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ within the composite.

Figure 3: SEM-EDX elemental mapping images of C, N, Ti, Mo, and S on a particle.

Figure 4: EDX spectra and elemental composition.

SEM–EDX analysis reveals a C/N-rich composition with minor Mo and S contents, yielding 43.9 at.% C, 52.1 at.% N, 1.1 at.% Mo, 2.6 at.% S, and trace Na (0.3 at.%).

EDX elemental mapping reveals the presence of a polymeric carbon nitride matrix characterized by a homogeneous distribution of carbon and nitrogen across the analyzed area. Molybdenum is detected at low overall concentration and appears as spatially localized domains embedded within this matrix rather than being uniformly dispersed, indicating that Mo is present as discrete surface-modifying species. Importantly, the Mo signal shows a clear spatial correlation with sulfur, consistent with the formation of $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ domains anchored to the carbon nitride surface. The absence of isolated Mo-rich or S-deficient regions rules out metallic or oxide Mo species and gives evidence for a configuration in which $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ is integrated as a surface modification rather than a bulk phase. Overall, the mapping demonstrates that carbon nitride serves as the dominant host phase, while $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ is present as finely dispersed, interfacially coupled domains within the carbon nitride matrix

3.3 $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ Preparation and IR Characterization

$(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was synthesized according to Dave et al. and further used to synthesize $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ following the procedure proposed by Fedin et al.^{[3][4]}. Attenuated total Reflectance-Fourier transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) was carried out on a Bruker Alpha II FTIR spectrophotometer containing a Diamond crystal ATR unit. The data was recorded with 24 scans at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and the spectrum was background-corrected within the Bruker OPUS 8.1 program suite.

Figure 5: ATR-FTIR spectrum of $\text{Na}_2[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}] \cdot 5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

4 Photonic Evaluation

4.1 Physical optics raytracing optimization

To maximise the efficiency of the photoreactor, a comprehensive optical optimisation procedure was conducted to determine the optimal geometry of the concentrating mirror surfaces. This procedure employed an optimisation algorithm that iteratively evaluated the performance of alternative design configurations using physical-optics-based ray tracing. The simulations were carried out using the RadiCal framework,^[5,6] which enables detailed modelling of light trajectories represented as discrete “light particles” spanning the entire global solar radiation spectrum from 250 nm to 2500 nm.

The optimisation target was to achieve the highest solar yield for global radiation with less than 400 nm on a non-tracking, stationary collector design. A detailed angularly resolved, time-integrated irradiance profile for the specific location was derived based on the geographic location, TMY climate data, and the application of the Perez-sky model. By relying predominantly on electrodynamic models, the applied physical optics approach captures a wide range of optical phenomena that are commonly neglected or oversimplified in conventional geometrical ray-tracing methods. These effects are, however, critical for accurately predicting the performance of photoreactors, particularly under natural illumination conditions. In the following, essential optical effects and their relevance for photo reactors are briefly highlighted:

Angular dependence of reflection and transmission

The integration of diffuse and specular reflective mirrors with transparent glass components leads to multiple scattering events, including multiple reflections and refractions. Accurate modelling of light propagation therefore requires precise calculation of reflection and refraction angles as well as their corresponding intensities. This, in turn, necessitates consideration of the wavelength-dependent optical properties of the material interfaces involved.

Refraction at solid–liquid interfaces

While many ray-tracing approaches are limited to modelling air or vacuum interfaces, accurate simulation of the photoreactor requires explicit treatment of refraction at the glass-liquid interfaces, i.e. the internal medium and cooling water interfaces. The RadiCal framework inherently supports this by incorporating appropriate refractive index models for the glass, water, and medium, enabling a realistic representation of light propagation within the reactor.

Polarisation

Polarisation effects arise during every reflection and refraction event and must be explicitly considered, as the polarisation state strongly influences subsequent scattering behaviour. Light reaching the photocatalyst typically undergoes multiple scattering processes, including repeated reflections at mirror surfaces and refraction and reflection events at the reactor's glass-air and glass-liquid interfaces. Neglecting polarisation therefore leads to significant inaccuracies in the predicted light paths and, consequently, in the estimated optical efficiency of the system.

Spectral dependence of absorption

Accurate modelling of photon transport enables determination of the spectral composition of radiation absorbed by the individual system components, including the reactor glass, cooling medium, reaction medium, and catalyst. This approach not only allows quantification of the photonic efficiency of the photochemical reaction, but also facilitates modelling and subsequent optimisation of the thermal effects arising from solar radiation absorbed by each component.

4.2 Determination of Solar Power Input to Concentrator

While the detailed Perez irradiance model was employed for optimisation of the reflector geometry, a simplified approach based on the isotropic sky model was used to evaluate the efficiency of the experiments conducted in this study using on-site measured irradiance data. The weather station, located only a few metres from the photoreactor, recorded global horizontal irradiance (*GHI*), direct normal irradiance (*DNI*), and diffuse horizontal irradiance (*DHI*) with high temporal resolution.

In order to estimate the irradiance incident on the concentrator, the global tilted irradiance (*GTI*) was calculated for two virtual input planes of the collector. Based on the isotropic sky model, the time-resolved irradiance at the upper (horizontal) input plane is given by:

$$GTI_{TOP}(t) = DNI(t) \cdot \max(\vec{n}_{TOP} \cdot \vec{d}_{sol}(t), 0) + DHI(t) \quad (1)$$

Similarly, the irradiance at the front (vertical) input plane of the concentrator is expressed as:

$$GTI_{FRONT}(t) = DNI(t) \cdot \max(\vec{n}_{FRONT} \cdot \vec{d}_{sol}(t), 0) + \frac{DHI(t)}{2} + \frac{\alpha \cdot GHI(t)}{2} \quad (2)$$

GTI global tilted irradiance [W/m^2]
DNI direct normal irradiance [W/m^2]
DHI diffuse horizontal irradiance [W/m^2]
GHI global horizontal irradiance [W/m^2]

$\vec{n}_{TOP}, \vec{n}_{FRONT}$ *surface normal vectors of top and front planes*
 \vec{d}_{sol} *unit vector pointing towards the instantaneous solar position*
 \propto *albedo of the local environment*

4.3 Calculation of incident solar power at SLPR surface

The incident solar irradiation on a freestanding cylindrical reactor was estimated using an isotropic sky model based on the measured solar irradiance data of the respective experimental days. The reactor geometry was defined by a cross-sectional area of 0.0508 m² and a lateral surface area of 0.179 m². A vertical reference plane with a tilt angle of 90° and an azimuth angle of 180° was used to define the reactor surface normal. Diffuse sky radiation was assumed to be isotropically distributed, with 50% of the visible sky contributing directly and 50% attributed to environmentally reflected radiation, using a ground albedo of 0.2. Direct, diffuse, and reflected radiation contributions were evaluated for each time step and summed to obtain the instantaneous optical power, which was integrated over the full diurnal cycle.

The resulting daily irradiation energies for the configuration without collector were 1.75 MJ (19.09) and 1.47 MJ (22.09), while inclusion of the solar collector yielded 4.19 MJ (19.09) and 3.54 MJ (22.09). To derive representative mean optical powers for the experimental trials, the integrated daily energies were normalized to the full duration of one day, including night-time periods, by averaging over 24 h. This normalization resulted in mean global optical powers of 8.1 W (without collector) and 20.2 W (with collector) for 19.09, and 6.8 W (without collector) and 17.1 W (with collector) for 22.09, corresponding to an enhancement factor of approximately 2.4 due to the solar collector.

In a subsequent step, these reflector-enhanced mean optical powers were used as reference values to correct the experimentally measured time-resolved solar power profiles. The integral measured optical power values were normalized for each experimental day such that the time integral of the corrected power matched the corresponding reflector-inclusive daily irradiation energy. This procedure preserved the diurnal power distribution while ensuring consistency between the measured data and the irradiation model, yielding corrected mean optical powers representative for the duration of the experimental trials. Corresponding $P_{solar,UV,reactor} = 7.31$ mW (19.09.25) and $P_{solar,UV,reactor} = 6.85$ mW (22.09.25) incident to the reactor surface can be calculated. With the normalized spectral solar emission ($\lambda < 400$ nm, AM 1.5)^[7], an absorbed molar solar photon flux of 21.78 $\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (19.09.25) and

20.41 $\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (22.09.25) for the duration of the experimental trials was calculated, assuming that all photons incident to the reactor surface are absorbed.

4.4 Photon Flux Calculations ($\lambda < 400 \text{ nm}$)

Solar photon fluxes were determined using the spectral solar emission ($\lambda < 400 \text{ nm}$, AM 1.5)^[7]. The solar emission spectrum was normalized to an integrated value of 1 (see Figure 7). The spectrally normalized solar emission profile $I_{\text{norm}}(E)$ with E representing the photon energy was used to distribute the corresponding determined solar power over the photon-energy range E_{min} (3.0 eV, 400 nm) to E_{max} (4.43 eV, 280 nm), according to Eq. (3).

$$\int_{E_{\text{min}}}^{E_{\text{max}}} I_{\text{norm}}(E) dE = 1 \quad (3)$$

Figure 6: Normalized spectral solar emission $\lambda < 400 \text{ nm}$, AM 1.5.

The resulting spectral absorbed power density $P_E(E)$ was obtained using the total corresponding solar power $P_{\text{solar,UV}}$ according to Eq. (4).

$$P_E(E) = P_{\text{solar,UV}} \cdot I_{\text{norm}}(E) \quad (4)$$

The corresponding spectral photon flux $q_E(E)$ was calculated by dividing the absorbed spectral power by the energy per photon ($e = 1.602 \text{ J} \cdot \text{eV}^{-1}$)

$$q_E(E) = \frac{P_E(E)}{E \cdot e} \quad (5)$$

The total absorbed photon flux (q_{tot}) was obtained by numerical integration of $q_E(E)$ over the considered photon-energy range.

$$q_{\text{tot}} = \int_{E_{\text{min}}}^{E_{\text{max}}} q_E(E) dE \quad (6)$$

q_{tot} was converted into a molar photon flux ($\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$) using Avogadro's constant N_A with Eq.(7).

$$q_{\text{tot},\mu\text{mol}} = \frac{q_{\text{tot}}}{N_A} \cdot 10^6 \quad (7)$$

5 Thermodynamic Assessment of Methanol-Assisted Photocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution

Definition of the Overall Reaction

For photocatalytic hydrogen evolution in a MeOH:H₂O mixture, methanol is commonly treated as a sacrificial electron donor while protons are reduced to molecular hydrogen.

Candidate reactions considered are:

Gas chromatographic analysis did not reveal the formation of CO₂. Therefore, reaction **B** is not supported by the experimental observations. Reaction **A**, corresponding to the partial oxidation of methanol to formaldehyde with simultaneous hydrogen evolution, is considered the relevant overall reaction.

Gibbs Free Energy for Reaction A

The standard Gibbs free energy change for reaction **A** is $\Delta G_r^\circ = +63.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ where ΔG_r° denotes the standard Gibbs free energies of formation of the respective species. All thermodynamic data were taken from *Atkins' Physical Chemistry*, 12th edition^[8]. The reported ΔG_r° corresponds to standard conditions (298 K, 1 bar) and was calculated according to Eq. (8).

$$\Delta G_r^\circ = \Delta G_{f,\text{HCHO}}^\circ + \Delta G_{f,\text{H}_2}^\circ - \Delta G_{f,\text{CH}_3\text{OH}}^\circ \quad (8)$$

6 Sources

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